

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING POLITICAL EDUCATION SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: Pedagogical opportunities for developing political education skills in future teachers - this involves educating teachers as active and responsible citizens not only in their subjects, but also in social and political life. Political education plays a major role in forming conscious concepts of citizenship, equality, justice, freedom, legal and democratic values in students. The pedagogical opportunities of this process are developed in the following areas:

Keywords: Pedagogical approaches and methods, Development of thought and worldview, Political knowledge and ethics, Development of constructive and critical thinking, Practical exercises and increasing political activity, Political curricula and innovations

Main part: The teacher's main approach to providing political education should be aimed not only at familiarizing students with theoretical knowledge, but also at helping them understand modern political and social problems, think independently and develop a critical approach. In this process, interactive methods, discussions, role-playing games, and occasional debates can be widely used.

It is important for teachers to familiarize the future generation with information based on political worldviews, as well as to teach issues such as democracy, rights, and freedoms. It is necessary to provide future teachers with extensive knowledge of various political systems, changes in society, and global issues.

The formation of political ethics, social justice, and legal awareness plays an important role in the comprehensive development of future teachers. Political knowledge helps students make independent decisions and actively participate in political processes. In this regard, the main attention in the pedagogical process should be paid to the spiritual, moral, and legal behavior of young people.

Critical thinking is of great importance in developing political education skills in teachers. This skill teaches students to critically analyze, analyze various political sources and thoroughly evaluate the ideas that arise in them.

Innovative pedagogical technologies and curricula should be developed to teach political knowledge to future teachers more effectively. These programs will help to actively involve students in political issues and increase their civic responsibility.

To increase political activity in teachers, it is recommended that students use practical exercises, discussions, and international experiences. This will allow students to be ready for practice and develop their skills in participating in political processes.

According to its levels and characteristics, pedagogical excellence is determined by external and internal factors. The correspondence of the content of the pedagogical formation process to the characteristics of the profession, the possession of its quantitative and qualitative components, professional training and retraining of future teachers, the form of the educational process, the correspondence of the material and technical base to the educational tasks to be solved, and the requirements of the time are external factors. Internal factors include the expression of pedagogical skill from a physiological point of view, the appearance formed by leading analyzers or personality temperament, the system of nervous characteristics, strong personal socio-psychological qualities

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arising from the characteristics of pedagogical skill, the close connection of pedagogical skill with all mental activity and some dynamic characteristics of the personality, the dependence of pedagogical development on the characteristics of the nervous system and the temperament of the teacher. The study lists the positive qualities that a modern teacher should have: the future teacher of a higher educational institution should have modern knowledge, the best practice and pedagogical skills, the ability to form a set of appropriate research methods, pedagogical research tasks, the acquisition of theoretical research skills and practical experience, the creation of skills and their practical application in professional activities, curricula, textbooks and teaching and methodological manuals, electronic textbooks in the subjects taught. The study provides the main goal of pedagogical skills, which is to form future teachers' professional skills, creative abilities, communication culture, educational skills, technology, the primary potential of teacher skills; pedagogical skills teach observation, creativity, the secrets of self-mastery of advanced pedagogical experience, the process of learning and teaching; knowledge, skills and management competencies, the state of mind.

Today, competitive personnel are being prepared that meet all the requirements of the economy and the free labor market, which require excellent pedagogical skills from teachers. The world is paying serious attention to the development of pedagogical skills in our republic and in developed countries, as scientists-pedagogues working in this direction are a special problem. The study pays special attention to the self-determination of their professional and personal status, self-education, self-improvement, self-development, the essence and importance of self-awareness as a “specialist of the perfect level, multi-faceted mastery of pedagogical skills, as an important task of the future teacher. In modern pedagogy, the task of implementing all knowledge, experience and pedagogical skills is the implementation of the teacher's activities based on mutual dialogue, including the interests and needs of students, and the implementation of lifelong learning, which is recognized as important, with special attention to the individual.

Conclusion: The pedagogical possibilities of developing political education skills in future teachers contribute to the formation of a modern teacher not only as a provider of knowledge, but also as an active contributor to political and social processes in society. The role of a teacher in providing political education is not only to transfer knowledge, but also to teach students to be active, responsible and socially active in society.

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